

UTILIZATION OF AGRICULTURAL RESOURCE-SAVING TECHNOLOGIES IN CROP PRODUCTION

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Abstract. *In this article the discussions regarding growing crops, which are very important part of farming helps make sure there is enough food and that the state can take care of itself, where farmers main job is to give people good food are presented.*

Keywords: *Agricultural production, a negative impact, transition, energy, energy-resource-saving technologies, condition, further development, functioning of agricultural sector, preservation, restoration, soil fertility, environment, the rational use, production resources.*

It is important to suggest that farming can be affected by many things, some of which can slow down its growth. Switching to technologies that save energy and resources is very important for the future growth and success of the farming industry. Using new technology will help us protect the soil and environment, use resources wisely, and make the most of our farming opportunities. Growing crops is a very important part of farming. It helps make sure there is enough food for everyone to eat, and that the food is good quality and grown in a way that is good for the environment. A large portion of farmland in Russia is used to grow grains and legumes. Wheat is grown in about 70% of all fields for cereal crops, and so are barley, corn, and oats. Plant-growing products help people get food, give businesses materials to make things, and provide food for animals. Crops used to feed animals make up about 30% of all planted fields.

Improving how we grow crops is made easier by: making the soil better for plants, using new machines and tools, using chemicals and machines to help with farming, having skilled farmers, and using science to help with farming. We need to think about the plant growing industry, which is affected by natural conditions, the seasons, and the use of land for farming. Considering the things that affect how crops grow will help us produce more, make better crops, and keep growing crops using new, efficient methods. Resource-saving technologies are about using less soil disturbance, keeping plant leftovers on the ground, choosing the right crops to grow, using better crop varieties, taking steps to make the soil better, and combining different methods to save resources.

Crop protection methods are used to keep pests, diseases, and weeds away from crops. Crop rotation methods are used to make the soil better and prevent pests, weeds, and diseases. Drones, satellite pictures and phone apps are new ways to protect and rotate crops. Protecting crops means keeping them safe from pests, diseases, and weeds, while rotating crops means improving the soil and stopping pests, weeds, and diseases from coming back. Modern tools like drones, satellite pictures, and mobile apps are used to protect and rotate crops. Agricultural technology, or "agritech," includes many different tools and techniques that help farmers grow more food. This includes things like cars, robots, computers, space machines, flying machines, phones, and computer programs. To cut out a piece from a digital picture or printed photo to keep only a smaller part of the original. Cutting a digital picture is done by a tool in all picture editing programs. Producing things with less waste and pollution, which helps to prevent harm to the environment.

An approach to make things work better and faster. Making things in big factories and making them safer.

Resource efficiency means using the Earth's resources carefully and without harming the environment. Using resources in a smart way means doing things like fixing and reusing products, recycling materials, and designing things to be more environmentally friendly.

Technology helps us do many things easily, like setting reminders, talking to people, paying bills, and shopping without leaving home. "Today, the important types of technology are Artificial Intelligence (AI), which is changing industries with automation and data analysis; Information Technology (IT), which is important for managing data and digital infrastructure; and Biotechnology, which is making advances in healthcare and farming. Tractors are big machines used for farming. The tractor is very common on farms and comes in different sizes to work for all farms. The main job of a tractor is to pull farm equipment, but new tractors can also have different tools attached to them for all kinds of farming jobs.

Some examples of the technologies used in precision agriculture include:

1. semi-automated steered vehicles.
2. driving systems for tractors and agricultural machinery.
3. satellite crop monitoring.
4. sensors and agricultural drones.
5. equipment capable of dosing fertilizers.
6. technology for remote fleet management.

Sustainable farming means using methods that don't harm the environment and help reduce pollution. This is important for lowering greenhouse gas emissions. Thankfully, there are new farming technologies that can help farmers meet their needs and also reduce greenhouse gases. In this post, we will learn about new ideas that can help farming be better for the environment. According to the suggestions, it will require 70% more food because there will be more people. A new report from the the reliables sources suggest that more than 10% of the people in the world don't have enough food to eat. Severe weather like droughts and heavy rainfall damage crops and make less food. So, we need to focus on the new technologies and ideas that can change farming.

In today's research, resource conservation means taking steps to save and use materials, energy, and other things needed for production. Resource-saving technologies in domestic production are not being used because they are too expensive in terms of labor. In developed countries, it costs 2-3 times less to produce crop products than in our own country. Agricultural companies need to find ways to save money by using new, energy-efficient technology and using resources wisely. Resource-saving technologies are about using less soil disturbance, keeping plant leftovers on the ground, using smart crop rotation, picking strong crop types, making soil better, dealing with pests and diseases in a combined way. Studying scientific papers helps us find the best ways to use less resources when growing crops. This includes using modern and efficient machines, new technologies, and better ways to organize and manage resources.

Saving resources is difficult and involves many parts. Research on farms in different regions shows that each farm has the potential to reduce costs and increase production on their land. Setting up a good accounting and control system helps to find ways to grow. Using technologies to save resources in farming doesn't always mean buying new machines and equipment. First, we need to concentrate on using very good seeds, rotating crops, following farming practices, and using resources wisely. Saving resources is complicated and has many parts. Studies of farms in different areas have shown that each farm has ways to save money and produce

more crops. This means they can lower their costs and get more crops from the same amount of land.

New farming techniques use less energy and help protect the soil. They focus on making the soil more fertile and using low-cost methods that don't rely on machines. Direct sowing seeders help you plant crop seeds at the right depth without disturbing the ground cover. The study found that to get consistent and reliable crops, farmers need to adjust the no-till system to fit their specific farming conditions. The biggest challenge is getting crops to grow in the fall after a non-fallow crop. This technology will help use less energy for plowing the land.

In conclusion it should be mentioned that creating a good system for accounting and controlling helps us see where we can grow. Using technologies to save resources in farming doesn't always mean buying new equipment, for which we need to use good seeds, change the crops we grow, follow farming rules, and use resources wisely.

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